

Repository to: IgE-mediated mast cell responses to rocuronium: a matter of protonation status.

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Repository methods

Patient inclusion

Sera obtained from patients with a suspected perioperative hypersensitivity (POH) reaction potentially related to rocuronium were included. All participants underwent a complete diagnostic workup including all potential culprits as described elsewhere (1). This workup, performed between 2 weeks and 24 months after their index reaction, started with STs with rocuronium, quantification of sIgE rocuronium and/or morphine, the latter considered an established biomarker of sensitization to tertiary and quaternary substituted ammonium structures that are part of the major epitope of rocuronium, and a BAT with rocuronium. As indicated in [Repository table R1](#), for this study, rocuronium allergic patients were defined as those with a combined positive ST to rocuronium, positive sIgE to rocuronium and/or morphine and a positive BAT to rocuronium. Exposed controls were defined as individuals who experienced a POH but were entirely negative for ST and BAT to rocuronium and negative for sIgE to morphine and/or rocuronium. All participants gave written informed consent, and the study was approved by the Ethical Committee of the Antwerp University Hospital (Belgium B300201316408). Samples were registered and stored in the local biobank (ID: BE 71030031000).

Skin tests

Rocuronium STs included skin prick tests (SPTs) to rocuronium (Esmeron®; Merck Sharp & Dohme, Brussels, Belgium) and, if negative, complementary intradermal tests (IDTs) to rocuronium. The maximum test concentration was 10 mg/mL (undiluted) for SPTs and 0.05 mg/mL (1:200 dilution) for IDTs, with dilutions prepared immediately before use. SPTs with a wheal >3 mm with surrounding erythema after 15 min were considered positive. For IDTs, reactions were read after 20-30 min. Intradermal reactions with a wheal and flare >8 mm (or doubling of the injection bleb) were considered positive. Negative control (saline buffer) and positive control (histamine 10 mg/mL; HAL Allergy Benelux NV, Haarlem, the Netherlands) were also tested.

Total and specific IgE antibodies

Total IgE and sIgE to rocuronium and/or morphine, were quantified using the FEIA ImmunoCAP system (Phadia Thermo Fisher, Uppsala, Sweden) according to the

manufacturer's instructions. The decision threshold for rocuronium and morphine was set at 0.13 and 0.35 kUA/L respectively, as calculated elsewhere (2).

Basophil activation test

The BAT for rocuronium was performed as described in (3). Briefly, heparinized whole blood was stimulated for 20 min at 37°C with serial dilutions of rocuronium bromide (Esmeron®; Organon) or anti-IgE or buffer as positive and negative controls, respectively. Dilutions were performed in IL-3-containing stimulation buffer (2 ng/mL, BD Biosciences). Reactions were stopped by placing the cells on ice and adding cold PBS containing 10 mM EDTA. For flow cytometric quantification of basophils, cells were stained with anti-human CD123, anti-human leukocyte antigen DR (HLA-DR), anti-human CD63 and anti-human CD203c for 20 min in the dark, on ice. Red blood cells were lysed, and white blood cells were fixed (FACS Lysing solution, BD) for 20 min at room temperature. After centrifugation, the cells were washed and resuspended in PBS containing 0.1% sodium azide. Flow cytometric characterization of basophils was based on a combination of side scatter, CD123⁺, HLA-DR⁻ and CD203c⁺. Results were expressed as the net percentage of CD63⁺ basophils (i.e., % rocuronium minus % buffer), and the threshold for positivity was set at 4%, as previously calculated by ROC analysis (3).

Standard passive human mast cell activation test (hMC-pMAT)

A detailed description of our "standard" hMC-pMAT rocuronium can be found in (1). Briefly, peripheral blood cultured MCs (PBCMCS) were cultured from CD34⁺ progenitor cells obtained from peripheral blood of a healthy volunteer. Subsequently, PBCMCS were passively sensitized with thawed patient sera (alkaline pH=7.9) overnight in a humidified CO₂-incubator at 37°C. The sensitized PBCMCS were pre-incubated for 20 min at 37°C with interleukin (IL)-33 (100 ng/mL) to prime IgE-mediated activation/degranulation (4). The pre-incubated PBCMCS were stimulated with Tyrode's buffer with NaHCO₃ (Sigma-Aldrich) as a negative control, anti-IgE as a positive control, or with the optimal stimulation concentration of rocuronium bromide (1000 µM, dissolved in Tyrode's buffer with NaHCO₃, pH=6.7 with final pH of 7.3, for 20 min at 37°C). The reactions were stopped by placing the cells on ice. The supernatants were then removed by centrifugation and the cells were stained with monoclonal anti-human CD117-APC (clone 104D2; BD Biosciences), anti-human CD203c-PE-Cy7 (clone NP4D6; eBioscience), and anti-human CD63-FITC (clone H5C6; BD Biosciences) for 20 min 4°C followed by fixation (BD

Phosflow™ Lyse/Fix buffer 5x, BD Biosciences) for 20 min at room temperature. Finally, the cells were washed and resuspended in phosphate-buffered saline containing 0.1% sodium azide and analyzed by flow cytometry. Degranulation of PBCMCs was measured as surface up-regulation of the lysosomal degranulation marker CD63 and up-regulation of CD203c density as an activation marker. The diagnostic threshold was set at 3% up-regulation of CD63, i.e., expression of the negative control + 3.3 SD (1).

Acidified hMC-pMAT (hMC-pMAT^{AC})

To study the effect of acidification on MC responsiveness, Tyrode's buffer without the addition of NaHCO₃ was used to lower the pH. The pH of the Tyrode's buffer was adjusted with HCl where needed to obtain the desired pH at the start of the stimulation. Cell viability was checked with the LIVE/DEAD™ Fixable Near-IR Dead Cell Stain Kit (Thermo Fisher Scientific).

To study the effect of removing NaHCO₃ from the Tyrode's buffer, the hMC-pMATs were performed with and without the addition of NaHCO₃ to the Tyrode's buffer. The concentration of NaHCO₃ added to the Tyrode's was 27 mM, comparable to the NaHCO₃ concentration in plasma (25.7 ± 3.7 mM) (5). The pH of the Tyrode's buffer without NaHCO₃ was adjusted with HCl to obtain the desired predetermined pH at the start of the stimulation.

Calcium experiments

Since lowering of the pH causes an increase in free Ca²⁺, approximately 0.2 mM from pH 7.3 to 6.9 (6), in a separate set of experiments, CaCl₂ was added to the standard hMC-pMAT setting (pH 7.3) to raise Ca²⁺ concentrations by 0.1, 0.2 and 0.4 mM. As approximately 50% of the calcium could also bind to serum proteins, the highest concentration of added CaCl was set at 0.4 mM.

Flow cytometry

Flow cytometry was performed on a FACSCanto II™ flow cytometer (BD Immunocytometry Systems, San Jose, CA, USA) equipped with three lasers (405, 488, and 633 nm). Correct compensation settings for fluorochrome-conjugated antibodies were performed using BD™ CompBeads (BD Biosciences). Flow cytometric data were analyzed using Kaluza Analysis 2.1 software (Beckman Coulter, Brea, CA, USA) and FCS Express 7 Research edition (De Novo Software, Pasadena, CA, USA). A fluorescence minus one (FMO) was used to differentiate between positive and negative cells. PBCMCs were gated as CD117 and CD203c double

positive cells (CD117⁺CD203c⁺). GraphPad Prism version 10 (GraphPad Software Inc., San Diego, CA, USA) was used for data analysis.

Statistics

GraphPad Prism version 10 (GraphPad Software Inc.) was used for data analysis. Friedman's test with Dunn's multiple comparison test was used for [Figure R1](#) and [R5](#). Wilcoxon matched-pairs signed rank test was used for [Figure 1](#) and figures [R2](#), [R3](#) and [R4](#).

Repository figures and tables

Figure R1. Effect of pH on the passive mast cell activation test (hMC-pMAT) with rocuronium.

Donor MCs were passively sensitized with sera from 5 rocuronium allergic patients and subsequently stimulated with rocuronium (1000 μM) under different pH conditions (7.3, 6.9, 6.6 and 6.2). The horizontal black lines represent the median values. The horizontal dashed line represents the diagnostic threshold for hMC-pMATs which was set at 3%, i.e., expression of the negative control + 3.3 SD (1). Statistics: Friedman's test with Dunn's multiple comparison test.

Figure R2. Comparison of the standard hMC-pMAT and acidified hMC-pMAT (hMC-pMAT^{AC}) with the positive control anti-IgE.

hMC-pMAT results of donor MCs passively sensitized overnight with sera from rocuronium allergic subjects (black symbols, n=15) or exposed controls (red open squares, n=5) and challenged with the positive control anti-IgE. Each black symbol represents a serum from a single patient. Horizontal black lines represent the median values. Statistics: Wilcoxon matched-pairs signed rank test.

Figure R3. Comparison of the standard hMC-pMAT and acidified hMC-pMAT to rocuronium in CD203c. CD203c results are expressed as the Molecules of Equivalent Soluble Fluorochrome (MESF). hMC-pMAT results of donor MCs passively sensitized overnight with sera from rocuronium allergic subjects (black symbols, n=16) or exposed controls (red open squares, n=5) and challenged with rocuronium (1000 μ M). Each black symbol represents serum from an individual patient. Horizontal black lines represent median values. Statistics: Wilcoxon matched-pairs signed rank test.

Figure R4. Comparison of hMC-pMAT^{AC} rocuronium with and without NaHCO₃ added to the Tyrode's buffer.

Donor MCs were passively sensitized with the sera from 5 rocuronium allergic patients and were stimulated with rocuronium (1000 μ M). Statistics: Wilcoxon matched-pairs signed rank test

Figure R5. Effect of free Ca²⁺ variation on standard hMC-pMAT to rocuronium.

Donor MCs were passively sensitized with sera of 5 rocuronium allergic patients and were stimulated with rocuronium (1000 μ M) in the presence of the indicated concentration of free Ca²⁺. Statistics: Friedman's test showed no significant differences.

	Patient no.	Sex	Age (yr)	Ring and Messmer Classification	Acute tryptase ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Basal tryptase ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	MCA	Total IgE (kU/L)	slgE Rocu (kAU/L)	slgE morphine (kAU/L)	pMAT (%CD63+)	pMAT ^{AC} (%CD63+)
Low-responders	P1	M	70	4	108	7.50	Yes	93	0.13	2.95	19	38
	P2	F	67	3	N.D.	5.80	N.D.	193	0.76	4.10	13	29
	P3	F	48	4	102	4.19	Yes	183	<0.1	3.19	4	7
	P4	F	54	3	136	8.30	Yes	499	6.72	16.8	1	1
	P5	M	34	3	200	5.29	Yes	473	0.30	32.8	1	4
	P6	M	78	3	200	25.40	Yes	53	<0.1	0.92	2	9
	P7	F	17	N.D.	11.00	2.10	Yes	113	0.43	3.12	0	0
	P8	F	40	3	11.90	3.00	Yes	24	0.17	2.92	8	12
	P9	F	27	4	34.00	2.48	Yes	73	<0.1	7.80	1	2
	P10	F	53	3	4.40	6.90	No	110	0.34	1.94	2	3
	P11	F	70	4	111	7.60	Yes	40	<0.1	0.62	5	16
	P12	F	25	3	22.60	4.60	Yes	226	2.86	5.53	12	24
High-responders	P13	F	51	3	102	4.19	Yes	47	<0.1	0.53	21	17
	P14	F	74	3	48.00	4.60	Yes	33	0.42	0.19	51	33
	P15	M	67	3	67.70	11.20	Yes	253	0.36	3.47	47	22
	P16	F	57	3	108	9.20	Yes	51	0.12	0.39	27	20
Exposed controls	C1	F	57	3	33.30	N.D.	N.D.	146	<0.1	<0.1	1	0
	C2	F	74	3	3.30	3.00	No	14	<0.1	<0.1	0	1
	C3	M	16	2	N.D.	3.30	N.D.	14	<0.1	<0.1	0	1
	C4	M	49	3	115	14.20	Yes	73	N.D.	<0.1	1	1
	C5	M	67	4	10.70	7.70	No	9	N.D.	<0.1	1	0

Table R1: Characteristics of the patients and controls. All patients were ST and BAT positive for rocuronium. The 5 control subjects were ST and BAT negative for rocuronium. Mast cell activation (MCA) was defined according to the consensus formula: Acute tryptase greater than $1.2 \times$ baseline tryptase + $2\mu\text{g/mL}$ (7). Thresholds for slgE were set at 0.13 kUA/L for rocuronium and at 0.35 kUA/L for morphine (2). F, female; M, male; N.D., not determined; slgE, specific immunoglobulin E antibody; yr, year.

References

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